

ENA Genome Assembly Submission Practical

As we have discussed, there are three routes of submission:

- Interactive
- Programmatic
- Webin-CLI

In this exercise, you will have the opportunity to submit a dataset comprised of raw read data and an annotated assembly to the test version of the **ENA submissions** service.

Webin Submissions Portal (TEST): <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

You will need an ENA Webin account to use for this exercise. Webin accounts can be registered on the webin portal 'Register' page:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/accountInfo>

The screenshot shows the 'Webin Submissions Portal' registration page. At the top, there is a header with the ENA logo and the text 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE Webin Submissions Portal'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Account Management'. The main content area is titled 'Account Details' and contains several input fields for registration: 'Abbreviated center name', 'Full center name', 'Laboratory Name', 'Address', 'Country', 'Password', and 'Confirm Password'. Below these fields, there is a section for 'Contact Information' with a button that says 'Add At Least One Contact' and a plus sign icon. At the bottom, there is a section for 'No Sensitive Data' with a checkbox and the text 'I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.'

It will be helpful to review how the metadata model works. You can find an overview of this here:

[Metadata Model](#)

Throughout this exercise, you are asked to use the ENA test service, which allows you to make submissions which will be removed after 24 hours. If you're not sure if you're in the test server, you can check the address in your browser which will begin 'wwwdev' rather than 'www':

 https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

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The Scenario

You are contributing to an initiative aiming to produce reference genomes of pollinators. So you have sampled a bee, *Bombus digressus*. You have prepared a shotgun library for paired end sequencing on an Illumina HiSeq 2000. The result is a set of paired FASTQ files. You then proceed to use your assembly program to generate a reference assembly and subsequently annotate the genome. Now it is time to submit your valuable data to the ENA!

You will start by registering a project/study interactively, followed by registering one of your samples interactively. Then you will be submitting a set of paired fastq files (forward and reverse) and finally submitting your annotated assembly to the ENA test submission service using Webin-CLI. The test submission service is identical to the production submission service, but submissions are retained for <24 hours. It's therefore perfect for training settings like this.

Some of these exercises require use of the command-line. Where there is a command to run, it will be provided for you mostly complete, indicated by an indented line beginning with a dollar ('\$') sign. Do not enter the \$, just the text following it. Some commands have been left incomplete for you to fill in, so read them carefully before you enter them.

The Study

To begin, you should **register a study**. Recall that a study describes the purpose of the work you have done, groups other objects beneath it, and controls when the data becomes public. A study is required for all submissions to ENA.

1. Log in to the Webin test submission service with your account ID and the password:
<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>
2. After logging in, find the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Register study (project)**' button to see the study registration interface:

Register study (project)

Submission Details

Release date [This is when your study will be made public.] *

Short descriptive study title *

Study Name

Detailed study abstract *

Will you provide functional genome annotation ?

PubMed Citations Registration

Add PubMed Citations +

3. Set a **release date** for your study (this is when all data associated with the study will be released). This needs to be between now and a maximum of 2 years in the future.
4. The '**Study Name**' field should be filled in with something brief and meaningful that can help you find and recognise the study.
5. You should take time to provide a descriptive title and informative abstract for your own studies, but these can be edited later if needed. The title could be something similar to:
Genome assembly of *Bombus digressus* from <Your Town/Lab>
6. For submitting annotated assemblies you must click on 'Will you provide functional genome annotations'. This will then allow you to add a [Locus Tag Prefix](#) to your study. However, this function is disabled in the test environment, so you will not be adding that today.
7. When you have completed all required fields, click '**Submit**' and then confirm.
8. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Studies Report**' button to see the study you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.

Make a note of its accession numbers, which will resemble:

ERP##### and **PRJEB#####**

Note: For a real submission, these would be the numbers you would cite in any publications involving the data.

8. Find the appropriate taxon for your sample: to reiterate what we discussed during the presentation, please use a taxonomy that is as specific as possible.

- a. This can be looked up on our rest API. Here is an example of a search for “Bombus”. You can search for the relevant taxonomy by replacing “Bombus” in the url below:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/Bombus>

You can also search for the species name to find its tax ID on the NCBI Taxonomy database.

- b. NCBI Taxonomy database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

Note: For the submission of Genome assemblies of individuals or cultured isolates you must use a binomial scientific name with the flags:

```
"submittable" : "true",  
"binomial" : "true".
```

9. Give a 'Unique name' to your sample (sample_alias)

This value must always be unique among all samples submitted by your account and is a way for you to locate and recognise your specific samples.

10. Give your sample a title, this could look something like:

Bombus digressus sample from <Your Town/Lab/Location>.

11. Write a brief description for your sample

12. Fill out the remaining details.

Tip: You can always find out more about what a field means and what information it accepts by going back to the checklist fields page on the Webin Portal and reading their description and validation.

Collection date format (year-month-date): 2024-10-24 , 2024-10 , 2024

13. To complete the ‘specimen voucher’ field you should enter an unique identifier that references the physical specimen that is vouchered in a museum/biobank after analysis. The sample you analysed was vouchered in the ‘National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution’ in the Entomology Collection. To help you

construct this identifier you can use the [ENA Source Attribute Helper API](#) where you can search for the institution and collection and input the specimen identifier.

14. By the time you have completed this, your sample will be well-annotated and understandable to people finding it in the database later. Click on '**Upload filled spreadsheet to register samples**' on the Register Samples page and upload/submit the spreadsheet.
15. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Samples' tab to see the sample you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.
Make a note of its accession numbers as you will need these later:

ERS#####

The Read Data

Now that study and sample metadata have been registered, it is time to upload and submit the read data you have produced.

- file_R1.fastq.gz
- file_R2.fastq.gz

Let's say these are the raw read data files you have obtained as a result of sequencing your sample.

Submit Read Data using Webin-CLI

The next step is to register the read data produced by sequencing.

This will be done using the Webin-CLI program.

NOTE: You will require [Java version 17 or newer](#) for this exercise. If you do not have it on your computer, please install it.

Please have the [latest Webin-CLI version](#) installed.

1. Enter the following command on the terminal:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -help
```

This will output the list of options which can be used with this program. Explore these options to see how the program runs.

2. Now that you have had a look at the program, let's look at the FASTQ files you'll be submitting. There are two FASTQ files you have produced:

- file_R1.fastq.gz
- file_R2.fastq.gz

Ensure you are in the correct directory:

```
$ cd file/path
```

3. Next, you must have a manifest file. This file performs three functions:

- Indicates the names of files to submit
- Describes experimental metadata
- States the study and sample the data belong to

The ENA now accepts manifest files in TXT format and JSON format. TXT format is less likely to encounter format errors but if you are confident with JSON file format

and would like to give it a try, please go for it. Please prepare your manifest file in one of the formats shown below:

'manifest_reads.txt'

```
STUDY TO DO
SAMPLE TO DO
NAME TO DO
INSTRUMENT Illumina HiSeq 2000
INSERT_SIZE 300
LIBRARY_SOURCE TO DO
LIBRARY_SELECTION RANDOM
LIBRARY_STRATEGY TO DO
FASTQ TO DO
FASTQ TO DO
```

'manifest_reads.json'

```
{
  "study": "TO DO",
  "sample": "TO DO",
  "name": "TO DO",
  "instrument": "Illumina HiSeq 2000",
  "insert_size": "300",
  "library_source": "TO DO",
  "library_selection": "RANDOM",
  "libraryStrategy": "WGS",
  "fastq": [
    {
      "value": "TO DO.fastq.gz",
      "attributes": {
        "read_type": ["paired"]
      }
    },
    {
      "value": "TO DO.fastq.gz",
      "attributes": {
        "read_type": ["paired"]
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

4. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. Please download the file and fill out the fields missing (labelled as 'TO DO') from the manifest file:

- STUDY: enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)

- SAMPLE: enter an accession for the sample you registered earlier (ERSxxx)
- NAME: give the experiment a unique name
- LIBRARY_SOURCE: [Check permitted values for library source](#)
- INSTRUMENT: Illumina HiSeq 2000
- INSERT_SIZE: 300
- LIBRARY_SELECTION: RANDOM
- LIBRARY_STRATEGY: WGS
- FASTQ: enter the name and file path of the first sequence file
- FASTQ: enter the name and file path of the second sequence file

5. Now you have everything you need to submit your sequence data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context reads -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -validate
```

If you are using the JSON manifest you need to update the file extension.

Note: The -validate command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

6. Finally, it's time to submit the sequence files, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context reads -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -submit
```

7. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided accessions for your experiment and run objects. Note these down and your submission is complete.

The Genome Assembly Data

The final step is to submit your assembly. You will again use Webin-CLI to do this.

In this scenario, you have produced an annotated genome and your analysis file needs to be in [EMBL flatfile format](#). You will also require a manifest file in json or txt format:

- `Bombus_digressus_annotated_assembly.embl.gz`
- `manifest_assembly.txt`

Submit Genome Assembly Data using Webin-CLI

1. Ensure you are in the correct directory containing the downloaded files

```
$ cd file/path
```

2. Take a look at the contents of the file using the 'zcat' command:

```
$ zcat Bombus_digressus_annotated_assembly.embl.gz
```

Note: If you are using windows, you will need to gunzip the file and open it with notepad++

This is your annotated assembly file in the form of an EMBL flatfile.

3. Next, you must have a manifest file similar to the reads manifest. This assembly manifest:

- Indicates the name of the flatfile to submit
- Describes assembly metadata
- States the study, sample and run the data belongs to

Prepare the manifest file in the following format:

```
'manifest_assembly.txt'
```

```
STUDY          TO DO
SAMPLE         TO DO
RUN_REF        TO DO
ASSEMBLYNAME   TO DO
ASSEMBLY_TYPE  clone or isolate
COVERAGE      90
PROGRAM        TO DO
PLATFORM       ILLUMINA
FLATFILE       TO DO
```

4. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. There are five "TO DO" values which you must fill out:

- STUDY enter the accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)
- SAMPLE enter the accession for the sample you registered earlier (ERSxxx)
- RUN_REF enter the run accession you obtained in the previous exercise (ERRxxx)
- ASSEMBLYNAME enter a unique name for this assembly
- ASSEMBLY_TYPE clone or isolate
- Coverage 90
- PROGRAM enter the program used to assemble this genome (e.g. Flye_v2.9)
- FLATFILE the name and file path of the flatfile

5. Now you have everything you need to submit your sequence data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest XXX
-userName Webin-XXX -password XXX -test -validate
```

Note: The -validate command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

6. Finally, it's time to submit the embl flatfile, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.2.0.jar -context genome -manifest
XXX.txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX -test -submit
```

7. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided the accession for your analysis object. Note these down and your submission is complete.

Return to the interactive Webin interface and view the sample, run and analysis tabs to see the objects you submitted today:

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>